

D3.2 Cell characterization and combination with thermal management system technology

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-LC-BAT-10-2020 GA No. 963540
Project title	Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable EV battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility
Duration of the project	2021 – 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP3/T3.1
Document due Date:	30.03.2022
Actual date of delivery	20.03.2023
Leader of this report	Marco Amores, Daniel Koch, C. Andrés Pérez
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Report information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
1.1	12.09.2022	Marco Amores Daniel Koch	Draft version circulated to partners
1.2	07.02.2023	Marco Amores C. Andrés Pérez Daniel Koch Manuel Martínez Robert Albrecht	Final Version
1.3	08.02.2023		First confidential version reviewed by the coordinator and the WP leader
1.4	13.03.2023	Marco Amores C. Andrés Pérez Daniel Koch Manuel Martínez Robert Albrecht	Final Public Version

Executive summary

This report contains a summary of the work carried out in Task 3.1a, T3.1b and T3.5 within WP3. Specifically, these tasks focus on the electrical and thermal characterisation of the initial candidate battery cells, including modelling of their performance to feed BMS development activities in WP4, as well as the initial design of the cooling system for the battery pack refrigeration. Within the execution of these tasks, it has been found that the performance of the cells was in-line with manufacturer specifications. Additional experimental data has fed the electrochemical and equivalent circuit to reach precision below 30 mV.

Three different electrochemical models have been used to reproduce the cell behaviour. The validation process has shown the NTGK model to be the most suitable for the goals of the project. Five different discharge rates have been simulated: 0.05, 0.33, 0.5, 1 and 2 C. The maximum heat generated corresponds to the 2C rate discharge, with a value of 41 kW/m³, which is the most important information for the future design of the cooling circuit. A linear fit has also been obtained relating the total heat generated and the discharge rate.

In terms of electrical (voltage) response, a 2-RC-equivalent circuit model (ECM) has been developed. The parameters have been calculated based on the HPPC-measurement data (current pulse at different SoC-steps and operation points) by a least-squares algorithm. This resulted in a set of model parameters for every operation point (T, SoC, I), which can then be used to simulate the cell's electrical response at any driving profile. To assess the model accuracy, a WLTC profile was simulated for a representative cell, which showed satisfying results considering the 30 mV error window. In contrast, the ECM cannot predict the temperature evolution of the cell as accurate as the electrochemical model, which leads to the conclusion, that both models will be combined with their respective advantages to build an overall modelling approach with high accuracy.

The TMS can be characterised by a top and bottom cooling design. With aluminium fins in between the cells a homogeneous temperature distribution can be achieved within the BP. Open cell aluminium foam can improve the thermal conductivity to fulfil the project requirements from the thermal standpoint.

Table of contents

Report information sheet	2
Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
List of figures	5
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations	8
Introduction	9
1. Electrical and thermal characterisation of cells	10
1.1 Capacity validation	11
1.2 Open Circuit Voltage (OCV)	13
1.3 Rate Capability	15
1.4 Cycling performance.....	20
1.5 Cycling under WLTC conditions	24
1.6 Internal resistance	24
1.7 Continuous UFC	26
2. Cell modelling	31
2.1 Electrochemical Model	31
2.2 ECM.....	45
3. Thermal Management System	51
4. Conclusions	59
5. References	60

List of figures

Figure 1: Cell main specifications.....	10
Figure 2: Cell connection details and revision of the solutions implemented to connect the cells to test benches.	11
Figure 3: Test sequence - capacity validation.....	11
Figure 4: Voltage evolution during charge and discharge of the MB013 cell at C/3 charge.	12
Figure 5: OCV evolution as obtained from GITT tests for MB013 cell at 25 oC. Charge curve is depicted by round markers with the discharge curve marked with triangles.	13
Figure 6: OCV evolution obtained from very low current OCV measurement for MB005 cell at 10°C.....	13
Figure 7: OCV curve obtained from very low current OCV measurement for MB005 at 10 °C and considering the cycling effect after each iteration.	14
Figure 8: OCV curve as obtained from GITT tests for MB013 cell at 25°C and considering the cycling effect after each iteration.....	14
Figure 9: Test sequence - rate capability (discharge at different C-rates).....	15
Figure 10: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, 2 C-rates and considering the cycling loops.	19
Figure 11: Test sequence for a continuous cycling at 1C (140 cycles per round).	20
Figure 12: Test sequence for a continuous cycling at 0.5C (125 cycles per round).	21
Figure 13: Discharge capacity evolution for cell MB013 cycled at 1C at 25 oC.	22
Figure 14: Discharge capacity evolution for different cells cycled at 1C and 0.5C at three temperatures 10 °C, 25 °C and 40 °C.	23
Figure 15: Internal resistance evolution as a function of SoC for cell MB003 at 10 °C during charge (1C) and discharge (1C).....	25
Figure 16: Internal resistance evolution in function of SoC for the MB013 cell at 40 °C during Charge (1C) and discharge (1C).....	25
Figure 17: Internal resistance evolution in function of SoC for the MB013 cell at 25 oC during Charge (1C) and discharge (1C).....	25
Figure 18: Capacity evolution of two tested cells under fast charge conditions	26
Figure 19: Test sequence - UFC cycling generation 1.....	27
Figure 20: test sequence - UFC cycling generation 2.....	28
Figure 21: second generation of UFC cycling based on WLTC cycles with "in-between" fast charging.....	29
Figure 22: close-up of the WLTC cycling - 4 WLTC cycles are executed in a row; followed by a (slow) recharge to 80 % SoC. After 2000 km, a fast charge is performed.....	30
Figure 23: Sketch of the cell with temperature sensors location.....	31
Figure 24: Models comparison for the time evolution of the cell potential at 1 C.	32
Figure 25: Models comparison for the time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 1 C rate.....	33
Figure 26: Time evolution of the cell potential at 1 C rate.....	34
Figure 27: Time evolution of the state of charge at 1 C rate.	34
Figure 28: Time evolution of the heat generated at 1 C rate.	35
Figure 29: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 1 C rate.	35
Figure 30: Time evolution of the cell potential at 2 C rate.....	36
Figure 31: Time evolution of the state of charge at 2 C rate.	37
Figure 32: Time evolution of the heat generated at 2 C rate.	37
Figure 33: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 2 C rate.	38
Figure 34: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.5 C rate.....	39
Figure 35: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.5 C rate.	39
Figure 36: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.5 C rate.	40
Figure 37: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.5 C rate.	40
Figure 38: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.33 C rate.....	41
Figure 39: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.33 C rate.....	41

Figure 40: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.33 C rate. 42

Figure 41: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.33 C rate. 42

Figure 42: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.05 C rate..... 43

Figure 43: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.05 C rate..... 43

Figure 44: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.05 C rate. 44

Figure 45: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.05 C rate. 44

Figure 46: Second order polynomial fit of the maximum heat generated vs the discharge rate. 45

Figure 47: ECM model with two RC-pairs used to represent the electrical cell behavior. 46

Figure 48: exemplary model result: simulated vs. measured voltage response and voltage-difference of cell MB003 (10 °C) for a charge current pulse of 1 C. 47

Figure 49: exemplary model result: simulated vs. measured voltage response and voltage-difference of cell MB003 (10 °C), for a discharge current pulse of 1C..... 47

Figure 50: ECM model implementation in Matlab/Simulink - the model parameters are chosen based on the operation point (T, SoC) and the current input. 48

Figure 51: real driving cycle applied to cell MB003: simulation vs. measurement..... 49

Figure 52: real driving cycle applied to cell MB003: voltage delta = simulated - measured voltage. 49

Figure 53: Audi e-tron 55 battery pack 95 kWh battery pack exploded view 51

Figure 54: Constructive differences between prismatic cells and pouch cells 52

Figure 55: Cooling concepts based on thermal conductivity and area. 52

Figure 56: Solution matrix for different TMS concepts. 53

Figure 57: Comparison matrix of different cooling concepts. 55

Figure 58: Cooling concept on cell level exploded view. 55

Figure 59: Cooling concept on module level exploded view without module housing. 56

Figure 60: 3D Simulation of UFC at module level for aluminium fin cooling concept carried out with AVL-FIREM. 57

Figure 61: Thermal simulation of modules on battery pack level with module housing. 58

List of tables

Table 1: Charge and discharge capacities of different cells measured at two different temperatures (25 and 40°C) at C/3 with CCCV charging protocol.....	12
Table 2: OCV values for the NCM cell from specifications, GITT and qOCV laboratory tests. ..	14
Table 3: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and at BoL.	16
Table 4: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 1st cycling loop.....	17
Table 5: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 2nd cycling loop.	17
Table 6: AVG discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at two temperatures ,1C-rate and considering cycling loops.	19
Table 7: Discharge capacities during continues cycling of the cells at two temperatures (25 and 45 oC) and two cycling rates (0.5C and 1C).	22
Table 8: Linear fit of different cells with the estimation of cycles to reach SoH 80%.	23
Table 9: Changes in temperature considering the cycling loops and changes in SoC of the cells when the WLTC profile is applied.....	24
Table 10: Maximum heat generated at different discharge rates.....	45
Table 11: Comparison of cooling concepts based on thermal conductivity and area.....	53
Table 12: Parameters for thermal simulation on module level.....	56
Table 13: Parameters for thermal simulation on battery pack level.....	57

List of abbreviations

AI	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
AVG	<i>Average</i>
BMS	<i>Battery Management System</i>
BoL	<i>Beginning of Life</i>
BP	<i>Battery Pack</i>
ECM	<i>Equivalent Circuit Model</i>
EoL	<i>End of Life</i>
GITT	<i>Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique</i>
HPPC	<i>Hybrid Pulse Power Characterisation</i>
I	<i>Intensity</i>
IR	<i>Internal Resistance</i>
NMC	<i>LiNi_xMn_yCo_zO₂</i>
OCV	<i>Open Circuit Voltage</i>
SoC	<i>State-of-Charge</i>
SoH	<i>State-of-Health</i>
T	<i>Temperature</i>
TMS	<i>Thermal Management System</i>
UFC	<i>Ultra-Fast Charging</i>
WLTC	<i>Worldwide harmonized Light vehicles Test Cycles</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

In this deliverable a description and summary of cells' performance is benchmarked against manufacturer specifications, electrochemical and electrical modelling to analyse thermal behaviour and design an initial cooling system. A variety of electrical and thermal characterisations of cells has been carried out in form to assess their performance under relevant conditions. These results have been used to validate manufacturer specifications, create, and validate cell behaviour models, optimise UFC protocols and provide data/information to AI system.

1. Electrical and thermal characterisation of cells

A summary of cells specification is shown in Figure 1. It is of particular importance to validate cells' specifications as a first step and to further characterise the cells to assess their performance according to MARBEL project requirements. For the purpose of these tests, cycling rates are described in function of the cell's capacity with $1C = 150\text{ A}$.

Item	Parameters
Dimension, mm	44.3x220x101.6
Cell Capacity @ 25°C, 0.33C, Wh	150
Normal Operation Voltage (V)	2.8-4.35
Nominal Voltage, 0.33C, V	3.73
Nominal Energy @ 25°C, 0.33C, Wh	559.5
Cell Weight, kg	2.28
Energy Density, Wh/kg	245
Energy Density, Wh/L	565
DCR (25°C, 50%SOC, 10s), mΩ	0.65
Max Current (Discharge), 50% SOC, 10s, 25°C	900A
Fast Charge, 25°C, 5-80% SOC	22min
Charge Temperature	-20°C ~ 55°C
Discharge Temperature	-30°C ~ 55°C
Storage Temperature	-40°C ~ 60°C

Figure 1: Cell main specifications.

Cell connections

Since the cells used in the project were received from the manufacturer with raw tabs, no cable or any other connection to a test bench could be installed directly. Therefore, a solution to connect to the cells for the initial tests had to be found. In a first simple design, a cylindrical aluminium block has been welded to the cell tabs by laser welding technique in THI, which has been mentioned as the preferred welding option by the manufacturer upon request. Additional options, e.g., to screw cable terminals to the tabs, were investigated but finally discarded, since the thickness of the terminals was too small (only ~2 mm), thus a drilling and threading of the tabs would have led to a destruction of the cell. During the first attempt to connect the test cables to the welded block, the block teared off the tab, due to a limited welding seam thickness as well as limited mechanical stability. Therefore, in a second revision, an aluminium sheet metal with milled sliced holes was developed to on one hand reduce forces while fastening cables, on the other hand increase the current carrying surface by allowing more welding seems to be created. Due to a high thickness of the material, a bending subsequent to the milling was not possible. Therefore, in a third revision, the aluminium sheets to be welded were chosen in an L-shape and milled. This third approach shows promising results in a first cell test. More information can be found in the "deviations" section in this chapter.

Figure 2. Cell connection details and revision of the solutions implemented to connect the cells to test benches.

1.1 Capacity validation

First analyses performed focussed to confirm and validate that the full rated nominal capacity of 150 Ah and 559.5 Wh is reached. Cycling of the cells under isothermal conditions at 25 °C and a charge protocol where a constant current of C/3 to 4.35 V is applied followed by a constant voltage step at 4.35 V until the current falls below 7.5 A (C/20). A discharge process is then followed applying a constant current of C/3 to 2.8 V. Since the cell has been shipped, stored and have their tabs welded, the first 2 cycles have been considered conditioning cycles, with the third cycle considered as a stable one. Figure 4 shows the voltage profile of a representative cell (MB013) during charge and discharge, where a typical NMC/Graphite shape is observed (Guo, et al., 2022). The measured capacity in the range of 151-152 Ah is well in line with the 150 Ah specified in the manufactured datasheet. It shall be noted that the naming of the cells in the shown tables is according to the cell labelling that had been done after the cells arrived. The “MB” before the numbers means “MARBEL”; the full unique label for every cell is MARBEL-CELL-B1/27-01-2022/0xx, where “B1” means “Batch 1” with the delivery date, followed by the increasing cell number (1-50).

Figure 3: Test sequence - capacity validation

Figure 4: Voltage evolution during charge and discharge of the MB013 cell at C/3 charge.

Table 1: Charge and discharge capacities of different cells measured at two different temperatures (25 and 40°C) at C/3 with CCCV charging protocol. It shall be noted that the increased number of cells in the 25 °C batch is due to cells no. 4, 7, 9 and 49 being cells for the UFC tests, whereas cells 4 and 7 have reached their end-of-life in the first trial (see 1.7)

Capacity Validation		3rd cycle after conditioning			
		Charge (Ah)	Charge energy (Wh)	Discharge (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
10°C	MB005	137.3	537.9	137.2	511.0
	MB008	138.3	540.8	138.2	513.7
25°C	MB013	151.2	584.5	151.2	565.5
	MB014	151.0	585.8	151.4	566.1
	MB015	151.8	586.8	151.8	567.8
	MB016	151.5	586.5	151.6	567.0
	MB004	150.0	581.5	149.9	562.1
	MB006	151.3	585.7	151.1	565.1
	MB007	150.8	584.7	150.7	565.0
	MB009	150.3	583.0	150.1	562.7
	MB049	150.0	581.2	149.9	562.1
	40°C	MB019	151.9	587.2	151.8
MB020		152.1	588.0	152.1	569.0
MB021		151.7	586.6	151.6	567.3
MB022		151.9	587.3	151.9	568.3

1.2 Open Circuit Voltage (OCV)

The OCV is a key parameter on the battery performance, with a direct impact on the cell energy. The OCV of the battery derives from the cell chemistry employed, and manufacturers typically report a nominal OCV of the cell when the SoC of the battery is 50 %. Experimentally in the lab we have measure a OCV profile (Figure 5) via Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique (GITT) where relaxation periods are applied every 10% SoC variation to measure the true OCV of the cell. Additionally, a quasi-OCV curve over the entire SoC curve has been measured at low cycling rate (C/20), where the overpotential is low and the voltage is close to the real OCV curve. Table 2 summarise the values obtained for the OCV of the cells at SoC = 50%. The experimental results show a good agreement with manufactured specifications.

Figure 5: OCV evolution as obtained from GITT tests for MB013 cell at 25 °C. Charge curve is depicted by round markers with the discharge curve marked with triangles.

Figure 6: OCV evolution obtained from very low current OCV measurement for MB005 cell at 10 °C.

Figure 7: OCV curve obtained from very low current OCV measurement for MB005 at 10 °C and considering the cycling effect after each iteration.

According to the results obtained from cycling tests (Figure 8), the OCV curve tends to decrease its voltage value after each iteration compared to the results performed on the cell at BoL. These observations agree with our hypothesis, since due to the ageing effect, the cell reduces its capacity after each cycle.

Figure 8: OCV curve as obtained from GITT tests for MB013 cell at 25°C and considering the cycling effect after each iteration.

Table 2: OCV values for the NCM cell from specifications, GITT and qOCV laboratory tests.

	OCV at SoC = 50%	OCV after 125 cycles (0.5C) at SOC = 50%	OCV after 250 cycles (0.5C) at SOC = 50%
Cell specification	3.736 V	-	-
GITT test (discharge)	3.736 V	3.731 V	3.725 V
qOCV measurement (charge/discharge AVG)	3.716 V	3.712 V	3.716 V

The largest differences in terms of voltages are observed from SOC =0 % to SOC = 50% (Figure 8). As a cell is discharged and the SOC is reduced, it is more arduous to maintain the voltage of an aged in comparison with a cell at BoL.

1.3 Rate Capability

In order to assess the power capability of the cells to be used in the battery pack developed in MARBEL, a rate capability test has been carried out. This test is based on cycling the cell at different applied currents. In our case, a constant current to 4.35 V is applied followed by a constant voltage step at 4.35 V until the current falls below 7.5 A (C/20) is used during the charging step, followed by discharging steps at either 150 A (1C) or 300 A (2C).

Table 3 shows the measure capacities and energy of the measured cells. The discharge capacities and energy at 1C and 2C at 25 °C (148 – 151 Ah) show a good agreement with the manufacturer data sheet (nominal capacity 150 Ah). Rate capability test at 1C at 45 °C also show a good performance with >156 Ah capacity and energy >575 Wh. For the 2C test at 45 °C, however, our safety limit of 55 °C was reached in the welding seam, precluding to measure the full discharge capacity on this condition. It has to be noted that this temperature was reached on the welding seam, while the surface of the cells walls was below 50 °C, indicating this issue is related with the in-house welding solution and not to the intrinsic properties of the cells.

Figure 9: Test sequence - rate capability (discharge at different C-rates)

Table 3: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and at BoL.

Rate Capability (Fresh cells)		0.5C (75 A)		1C (150 A)		2C (300 A)	
		Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
10°C	MB003	133.8	493.9	132.2	479.4	/	/
	MB005	135.1	500.2	133.7	486.7	/	/
	MB008	136.2	503.2	135.5	492.5	/	/
25°C	MB013	/	/	149.0	547.9	150.1	539.1
	MB014	/	/	149.6	549.6	150.7	540.7
	MB015	/	/	149.7	550.3	150.7	540.9
	MB016	/	/	149.9	550.7	150.9	541.7
	MB004	148.6	554.7	146.4	539.6	/	/
	MB006	149.7	556.9	147.7	541.9	/	/
	MB007	149.3	556.9	146.9	541.3	/	/
	MB009	148.7	555.4	146.4	539.9	/	/
40°C	MB049	148.5	554.5	146.5	540.1	/	/
	MB019	/	/	156.8	579.0	Temperature reaches 55 °C	
	MB020	/	/	157.0	580.1		
	MB021	/	/	156.1	576.5		
MB022	/	/	156.0	576.1			

Table 4: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 1st cycling loop.

Rate Capability (After 1 st cycling round)		0.5C (75 A)		1C (150 A)		2C (300 A)	
		Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
10°C	MB003	131.4	484.8	129.6	469.1	/	/
	MB005	133.1	492.4	131.7	478.7	/	/
	MB008	134.4	496.3	133.7	485.4	/	/
25°C	MB013	/	/	146.7	538.6	147.9	530.1
	MB014	/	/	147.1	539.5	148.2	530.6
	MB015	/	/	147.9	542.9	148.8	533.4
	MB016	/	/	147.9	542.5	148.9	533.4
	MB004 (EoL)	85.2	310.8	76.8	272.1	/	/
	MB006	149.4	554.8	147.0	540.0	/	/
	MB007 (EoL)	63.3	231.3	45.9	158.2	/	/
	MB009 (UFC)	148.5	553.6	146.2	538.3	/	/
MB049 (UFC)	148.3	553.0	146.3	538.5	/	/	
40°C	MB019	/	/	153.8	566.5	Temperature reaches 55 °C	
	MB020	/	/	154.0	567.1	153.5	553.3
	MB021	/	/	153.6	565.6	153.1	551.9
	MB022	/	/	153.4	565.5	Temperature reaches 55 °C	

Table 5: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 2nd cycling loop.

Rate Capability (After 2 nd cycling round)		0.5C (75 A)		1C (150 A)		2C (300 A)	
		Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
10°C	MB003	125.9	459.6	124.5	445.6	/	/
	MB005	128.2	471.5	126.8	457.6	/	/
	MB008	133.0	490.0	132.4	479.7	/	/
25°C	MB013	/	/	144.2	527.9	145.4	519.6
	MB014	/	/	144.2	527.1	145.31	517.9
	MB015	/	/	145.6	533.5	146.8	524.6
	MB016	/	/	145.6	532.5	146.9	524.1
	MB004 (EoL)	cell ex.	cell ex.	cell ex.	cell ex.	/	/
	MB006	147.6	547.1	145.4	531.7	/	/
	MB007 (EoL)	cell ex.	cell ex.	cell ex.	cell ex.	/	/
	MB009 (UFC)	148.2	552.4	145.7	536.0	/	/
MB049 (UFC)	147.9	551.2	145.7	536.4	/	/	
40°C	MB019	/	/	151.2	555.7	150.7	541.8
	MB020	/	/	151.3	556.0	Temperature reaches 55 °C	
	MB021	/	/	151.1	554.5	150.7	540.6

	MB022	/	/	151.0	150.5	150.5	541.5
--	-------	---	---	-------	-------	-------	-------

Table 6: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 3rd cycling loop.

Rate Capability (After 3 rd cycling round)		0.5C (75 A)		1C (150 A)		2C (300 A)	
		Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
10°C	MB008	131.5	483.5	130.9	473.0	/	/
25°C	MB006	145.8	539.6	143.8	524.7	/	/

Table 7: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, three current rates and after 4th cycling loop.

Rate Capability (After 4 th cycling round)		0.5C (75 A)		1C (150 A)		2C (300 A)	
		Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)	Discharge capacity (Ah)	Discharge energy (Wh)
25°C	MB006	144.3	533.2	142.3	518.1	/	/

Results of 1C discharged capacity are compared in order to obtain a clear image of the ageing effect. The capacity is clearly affected after the cycling loops. According to the results obtained, in average the capacity is reduced -1.4% and -3.1% at 25°C after the 1st cycling loop and 2nd cycling loop, respectively. This capacity reduction is even more severe at 40°C, -1.8% and -3.4% after the 1st cycling loop and 2nd cycling loop, respectively. Energy reduction event is also shown in the test results and present similar values compared to the capacity decrease.

Figure 10: Discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at three temperatures, 2 C-rates and considering the cycling loops.

Table 6: AVG discharge capacities and energies measured on the rate capability test at two temperatures, 1C-rate and considering cycling loops.

	BoL		1st Cycling Loop		2nd Cycling Loop	
	1C Discharge Capacity (Ah)	1C Discharge Energy (Wh)	1C Discharge Capacity (Ah)	1C Discharge Energy (Wh)	1C Discharge Capacity (Ah)	1C Discharge Energy (Wh)
10°C – AVG	133.8	486.2	131.7	477.7	127.9	461.0
Delta	/	/	-1.6%	-1.7%	-4.4%	-5.2%
25°C - AVG	149.5	549.6	147.4	540.9	144.9	530.2
Delta	/	/	-1.4%	-1.6%	-3.1%	-3.5%
40°C - AVG	156.5	577.9	153.7	566.2	151.1	555.4
Delta	/	/	-1.8%	-2.0%	-3.4%	-3.9%

1.4 Cycling performance

Cycling life is a major performance parameter on the battery cells, that will determine the number of kilometres the battery will allow the EV to drive before the end of the battery first life in the car. To analyse the cycling life and degradation behaviour of the batteries, a continuous cycling test is being performed (Table 7). After 280 cycles at 1C and 250 cycles at 0.5C, the SoH is maintained above 94.0% at both temperatures, indicating no signs of premature degradation, even at 10 °C. The following diagrams show the test programs for the continuous cycling. The UFC cycle test sequence is shown in the respective section. Table 7 shows the current state of the cells under test (current capacity = most recently measured and SoH).

Figure 11: Test sequence for a continuous cycling at 1C (140 cycles per round).

Figure 12: Test sequence for a continuous cycling at 0.5C (125 cycles per round).

Table 7: Discharge capacities during continues cycling of the cells at two temperatures (25 and 45 °C) and two cycling rates (0.5C and 1C). SoH is calculated as the % ratio between capacity on 1st cycle and the last recorded cycle.

Continuous cycling	Cycling rate (C = 150 A)	1 st cycle discharge capacity (Ah)	Most recent discharge capacity	SoH	
10°C	MB003	1C	132.2	124.5 (280 cycles)	94.2
	MB005	1C	133.7	126.8 (280 cycles)	94.8
	MB008	0.5C	136.2	131.5 (375 cycles)	96.5
25°C	MB013	1C	148.7	146.5 (280 cycles)	98.5
	MB014	1C	149.2	146.0 (280 cycles)	97.9
	MB015	0.5C	151.5	148.8 (250 cycles)	98.2
	MB016	0.5C	151.2	148.5 (250 cycles)	98.2
	MB004	UFC (>2C)	146.4	cell ex.	0
	MB006	1C	147.7	142.3 (560 cycles)	96.3
	MB007	UFC (>2C)	146.9	cell ex.	0
	MB009	UFC (>2C)	146.4	145.7	99.5
	MB049	UFC (>2C)	146.5	145.7	99.5
40°C	MB019	1C	157.2	152.6 (280 cycles)	97.1
	MB020	1C	157.4	153.5 (280 cycles)	97.5
	MB021	0.5C	158.5	154.4 (250 cycles)	97.4
	MB022	0.5C	158.3	155.1 (250 cycles)	98.0

Two cells were tested until its EoL (MB004 and MB007), as both samples were used to validate the UFC scenario. All tested cells present similar behaviour in terms of discharged capacity reduction during the cycling.

Figure 13: Discharge capacity evolution for cell MB013 cycled at 1C at 25 °C.

Linear ageing is observed for all cells with 280 and 250 cycles (Figure 14). Taking this phenomenon into account, a linear fit is implemented to estimate the projection of the cells to reach SoH 80% (Table 8).

Figure 14: Discharge capacity evolution for different cells cycled at 1C and 0.5C at three temperatures 10 °C, 25 °C and 40 °C. For the shown cells at 10 °C MB003 and MB005, it shall be noted that after the first cycle round the cells were put at rest at 10 °C for approx. 2 months, which is shown by a capacity reduction of approx. 3 Ah.

Table 8: Linear fit of different cells with the estimation of cycles to reach SoH 80%.

Cell ID	Equation	R ²	Cycles to reach SoH 80%
MB003 (10°C - 1C)	$y = -0.0159x + 131.5$	0,987	721
MB005 (10°C - 1C)	$y = -0.0122x + 133.1$	0,985	1077
MB013 (25°C - 1C)	$y = -0.0138x + 148.96$	0,987	2099
MB014 (25°C - 1C)	$y = -0.0142x + 149.12$	0,993	2051
MB015 (25°C - 0.5C)	$y = -0.0156x + 151.62$	0,963	2027
MB016 (25°C - 0.5C)	$y = -0.0137x + 151.19$	0,9817	2277
MB019 (40°C - 1C)	$y = -0.02x + 156.87$	0,989	1844
MB020 (40°C - 1C)	$y = -0.02x + 157.14$	0,989	1857
MB021 (40°C - 0.5C)	$y = -0.0205x + 158.37$	0,972	1872
MB022 (40°C - 0.5C)	$y = -0.0191x + 158.07$	0,971	1993

According to these results and considering a vehicle which has an average consumption of 20kWh/100km, a complete battery pack containing MB013 cells will manage to complete around 910.000 km before SoH reaches 80% (it should be noticed that this cycling profile considers an aging effect produced under controlled and moderate conditions). It shall also be noted that for cells MB003 and MB005, the step in capacity decrease due to the rest at 10 °C is not considered in the linear fit equations in Table 8.

1.5 Cycling under WLTC conditions

To further analyse the performance of cells under relevant environment for the project, a simulated driving profile, WLTC, was applied to the cells, again, at three different temperatures. The WLTC cycling profile impact to the cells was analysed as a variation of their temperature and SoC decrease. Table 9 shows a maximum increase in temperature of 8°C during the driving profile, as well as a SoC decrease below 20%. The measured data will be compared to a simulated WLTC-cycle on the models derived from the characterisation tests, to validate their performance.

Table 9: Changes in temperature considering the cycling loops and changes in SoC of the cells when the WLTC profile is applied.

WLTC		Base Temp (BoL)	Max Temp (BoL)	ΔTemp (BoL)	ΔTemp (after 1 st cycling loop)	ΔTemp (after 2 nd cycling loop)	Discharged capacity (BoL)	SoC decrease (BoL)
		(°C)	(°C)	(°C)	(°C)	(°C)	(Ah)	(%)
10°C	MB003	9.8	11.7	1.9	2.0	2.2	20.9	13.9
	MB005	9.6	11.2	1.6	1.6	1.9	21.2	14.1
25°C	MB013	24.4	27.1	2.7	4.6	3.7	20.9	13.9
	MB014	24.6	30.9	6.3	4.0	3.0	20.9	13.9
	MB015	25.1	30.6	5.6	5.1	2.4	20.9	13.9
	MB016	25.4	30.0	4.7	8.0	2.4	20.9	13.9
40°C	MB019	40.8	44.5	3.6	3.5	3.7	20.9	13.9
	MB020	40.5	45.2	4.7	3.6	6.0	20.9	13.9
	MB021	40.6	44.8	4.2	3.5	5.2	20.9	13.9
	MB022	40.3	45.1	4.8	4.5	4.7	20.9	13.9

From the results obtained (Table 9) at 25°C no relationship can be observed between the temperature delta and the ageing effect due to the cycling loops, nevertheless, at 40°C the increase of temperature after the 2nd cycling loop is clearly more significant compared to a cell at BoL.

1.6 Internal resistance

Another important intrinsic parameter of the battery cell to its SoH, is the internal resistance. This is an indicator of the cell degradation and can also offer an indication of the SoC range at which the battery could work best, with less resistance to charge/discharge stress. Figure 17 shows the evolution of the internal resistance, as acquired by means of a Hybrid Pulse Power Characterisation, HPPC, test. The curve shows the usual valley-type shape for a NMC/Graphite cell chemistry (Guo, et al., 2022), with lower resistance values at intermediate SoC values and higher values at low and high SoC values. The internal resistance range is between 0.55 and 0.65 mΩ at BoL (Figure 17), in good agreement with the manufacturer reported internal resistance value of 0.65 mΩ at 25°C and 50% SoC.

Figure 16: Internal resistance evolution as a function of SoC for cell MB003 at 10 °C during charge (1C) and discharge (1C)

Figure 15: Internal resistance evolution in function of SoC for the MB013 cell at 40 °C during Charge (1C) and discharge (1C).

Figure 17: Internal resistance evolution in function of SoC for the MB013 cell at 25 °C during Charge (1C) and discharge (1C).

The internal resistance is increased after the cycling loops for discharge and charge tests. This resistance increase is directly related with a higher energy losses that will show an aged cell compared to a cell at BoL, leading to increase the heat that is generated in the aged cell. This IR increase is more severe after the 2nd cycling loop and between the range of 60-90% of SOC.

1.7 Continuous UFC

One of the requirements for the setup in MARBEL project, is the capability of the battery pack for ultra-fast charging. Based on first assumptions of cell properties coupled with the desired charging-power and -time, a charge current of slightly above 2 C, 320.5 A was deduced to be applied to the cells between 5 % to 80 %. Thus, the continuous fast charge cycle procedure was defined to repeat the fast recharge between 5-80 % SoC followed by a 1C discharge 25 times (at 25 °C ambient temperature), without a rest phase in between. After each of the sets of 25 cycles, a 4-hour rest phase was followed by a standard cycle and a discharge at 1 C, to track the capacity over the number of cycles. The whole procedure was repeated 20 times, to get a total number of 500 fast-charge cycles. Figure 18: Capacity evolution of two tested cells under fast charge conditions shows the capacity evolution of the two tested cells over the cycle number.

Figure 18: Capacity evolution of two tested cells under fast charge conditions

As shown by Figure 18, the cells reach their end-of-life way earlier than expected, which indicates that the charging profile must be adapted to avoid this fast aging. Thus, currently the measurement data is used to create a cell model and use it to optimize the charging profile, to reach the targeted number of cycles of > 2000. It shall be noted that the cell manufacturer doesn't give any indication about the number of fast charge cycles that can be achieved, the only specification is the SoC-range and the time that is required for the recharge (see data-brief above).

Figure 19: Test sequence - UFC cycling generation 1

In a second generation of UFC cycles, the profile was adapted to the requirements mentioned in the project's call: driving cycles with a WLTC profile, whereas between these cycles a standard charge with C/3 was performed. After every 2000 km, a fast charge from 5 – 80 % was performed with the abovementioned current (320.5 A). After 6000 km, two consecutive fast charges were performed. The following figure shows the test profile.

In the following figure, the test profile is shown.

Figure 20: test sequence - UFC cycling generation 2

Figure 21: second generation of UFC cycling based on WLTC cycles with "in-between" fast charging

The current spikes represent the fast charge phase; the profile in between is the WLTC cycling, which is adapted to the cell's current limits and the BEV-properties of the Benchmark vehicle Audi e-tron. The following pictures shows a zoomed view to a WLTC cycle.

Figure 22: close-up of the WLTC cycling - 4 WLTC cycles are executed in a row; followed by a (slow) recharge to 80 % SoC. After 2000 km, a fast charge is performed.

As shown in Table 7, the remaining capacity after 2 UFC-cycle rounds of second generation is at around 145,7 Ah. The distance in km at that time sums up to 12.000 km, which is calculated based on a distance per WLTC cycle of approx. 23 km. Per cycling round, 264 WLTC cycles are executed with the cells. Extrapolating these results with an approximate reduction of < 1 Ah per 12.000 km (linear assumption), the goal of 300.000 km seems reachable with the shown profile.

Thus, this profile will be applied to the new cells once arrived, since regular cycling data (discharge at different C-rates) is already available from the manufacturer. It will therefore be investigated, what effect the cooling system will have on the cell's life expectancy compared to the cycling in the temperature chamber with forced convection.

2. Cell modelling

2.1 Electrochemical Model

The goal of this task is to have a model able to predict the heat generated by the cell during the discharge process. This is important as the cooling system design will have to guarantee that all the heat generated can be removed to avoid overheating in the vehicle.

The software Ansys Fluent was used to perform the simulations. The Multi-Scale Multi-Domain method was used given its ability to solve the electrical and thermal fields simultaneously. Three different electrochemical models were tested for modelling the cell electrical and thermal behaviour: Newman pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D); Newman, Tiedemann, Gu and Kim (NTGK); and equivalent circuit model (ECM) (Vanaclocha, 2021). The P2D model is a physics-based model which solves the conservation equations for lithium and charge both in the electrolyte and solid phases. The charge and mass equations are coupled by the Butler-Volmer equation. This model is the most expensive in terms of computational cost out of the three but is the one providing a more physical meaning. The NTGK model is semi-empirical and uses some parameters which are dependent on the depth of discharge, which at the same time are computed via empirical constants. It is not as computationally expensive as the P2D model. Finally, the ECM is also a semi-empirical model where an electrical circuit simulates the behaviour of the cell. There are three different approaches to compute most of the variables of the system: with a function proposed by Chen, with fifth order polynomials and with a table of values which defines the different parameters as a function of temperature and the state of charge. The ECM, in any of its three forms, is the cheapest computationally among the models considered.

In order to choose the best model, validation was carried out with laboratory data at 1 C rate. Time evolution curves for potential and temperature were used for the validation. Once a model was chosen, additional simulations were run at four other discharge rates (2, 0.5, 0.33 and 0.05 C) and were also validated with experimental data. Figure 23 shows a sketch of the cell with four views (all faces except top and bottom) where the six temperature sensors are located. They are named CH13, CH14, CH15, CH16, CH17 and CH18 and are represented by orange rhombuses.

Figure 23: Sketch of the cell with temperature sensors location.

The experiments at the laboratory, reported in the previous section, were carried out in a climatic chamber. In order to avoid unnecessary complexity which would derive in even larger computational costs, the climatic chamber is not included in the simulation. To model the effect of the recirculating air stream in the chamber, the model assumes the cell is surrounded by air and a convection coefficient is used to model the heat transfer between the cell and the

surroundings. Different values for this convection coefficient are tested, as it is shown later in this section, and a value of $15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ yields the best overall match with the experimental data.

Figure 24 shows the time evolution of the cell potential at a discharge rate of 1 C. The black dashed line represents the experimental data, while the continuous lines refer to the different models used. They are sorted by computational cost, that is, the P2D model is the most expensive computationally, followed by the NTGK model and the ECM in their different variations. As it can be observed, the two best fits are obtained with the NTGK model and the ECM with Chen approximation, as they are the ones better representing the final moments of the discharge process. Since the main objective of this modelling is to predict the heat generated by the cell and not the exact behaviour during all the discharge process, validating the temperature evolution is key. Figure 25 shows the time evolution of the temperature at the CH13 sensor location for three different models and the experimental data. As it can be seen, the NTGK model is the one reproducing more accurately the temperature behaviour. Therefore, from the information shown in Figure 24 and Figure 25, the NTGK model is the one chosen to carry out the rest of the simulations at the different discharge rates previously mentioned.

Figure 24: Models comparison for the time evolution of the cell potential at 1 C.

Figure 25: Models comparison for the time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 1 C rate.

As it was previously mentioned, the effect of the climatic chamber is modelled via air convection coefficient (h in subsequent plots). Figures 26 to 29 show the results provided by the NTGK model at 1 C rate for the time evolution of the potential, state of charge (SOC), total heat source and temperature at the CH13 sensor location, respectively. Three different lines are shown for different convection coefficient values of 15, 30 and 50 W/m²K. Plots at the other five temperature sensors locations are not shown since they do not add any significant information to what is already shown in Figure 29. In Figures 26 and 29, experimental data is also shown. As it can be observed in Figure 29, a convection coefficient of 15 W/m²K shows the best agreement with the measured temperature evolution. As expected, its value has no influence on the potential and SOC evolution over time, and it is barely noticeable in the total heat generated. The maximum value for the heat generated discharging at a 1 C rate is 22 kW/m³.

Figure 26: Time evolution of the cell potential at 1 C rate.

Figure 27: Time evolution of the state of charge at 1 C rate.

Figure 28: Time evolution of the heat generated at 1 C rate.

Figure 29: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 1 C rate.

The results for a 2 C rate are shown in Figures 30 to 33. Two different convection coefficient values are plotted, 15 and 30 W/m²K. As it can be seen in Figures 30 to 33, both the potential and temperature behaviour at the beginning and end of the discharge process matches experimental data. However, the middle part of the process is not as accurate, especially for the potential. In addition, while a convection coefficient of 30 W/m²K seems to fit better the time evolution of the temperature (Figure 33), a convection coefficient of 15 W/m²K matches better at the end of the process. Given that the maximum heat generated takes place then, it is considered that convection coefficient of 15 W/m²K as the more useful for the purpose of these simulations. As expected, with a faster discharge the maximum value for the heat generated is larger than it was at 1 C. As it can be observed in Figure 32, the maximum value for the heat generated at 2 C is 41 kW/m³.

Figure 30: Time evolution of the cell potential at 2 C rate.

Figure 31: Time evolution of the state of charge at 2 C rate.

Figure 32: Time evolution of the heat generated at 2 C rate.

Figure 33: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 2 C rate.

Figures 34 to 37 show the results for a 0.5 C rate. In this case the convection coefficients tested are 10 and 15 W/m²K. The deviation in the temperature time evolution compared to the experimental data is less than one degree Celsius, but the reduced scale in the vertical axis may hint otherwise (Figure 37). Compared to the other two cases (1 C and 2 C rates), the shape of the time evolution of the heat generated is smoother and only increases abruptly towards the end of the process. The maximum value for the heat generated is 14 kW/m³.

Figure 34: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.5 C rate.

Figure 35: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.5 C rate.

Figure 36: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.5 C rate.

Figure 37: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.5 C rate.

The results for a 0.33 C rate are shown in Figures 38 to 41. The overall behaviour is similar to the one at 0.5 C rate. Again, the convection coefficients tested are 10 and 15 W/m²K. The starting and end points of the processes are more accurately represented than the middle part of the process, as it happened with the previous cases. The maximum value for the heat generated is 7 kW/m³.

Figure 38: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.33 C rate.

Figure 39: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.33 C rate.

Figure 40: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.33 C rate.

Figure 41: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.33 C rate.

Figure 42 to 45 show the results obtained for a discharge rate of 0.05 C. This time the convection coefficients tested are 15 and 30 W/m²K. However, as it can be seen, specifically in Figure 45, the differences at such low discharge rate are hardly noticeable. The maximum value for the heat generated is 1 kW/m³.

Figure 42: Time evolution of the cell potential at 0.05 C rate.

Figure 43: Time evolution of the state of charge at 0.05 C rate.

Figure 44: Time evolution of the heat generated at 0.05 C rate.

Figure 45: Time evolution of the temperature at CH13 sensor location for a 0.05 C rate.

Table 10 summarizes the maximum heat generated at different discharge rates, so it can be used to properly design the cooling system. As it can be seen, the faster the discharge rate the more heat is generated, as it was expected. Figure 46 shows a second order polynomial fit between the maximum heat generated and the discharge rate, according to the results obtained in the numerical simulations. A function of the form $y = -2.2864x^2 + 25.059x + 0.1354$, where y is the maximum heat generated in kW/m^3 and x is the discharge rate, is found to agree reasonably well with the results obtained in the simulations ($R^2=0.9945$). At a discharge rate of 0.05 C the fit deviates 17.6 % from the numerical simulations, while at 2 C the deviation is 0.3 %.

Table 10: Maximum heat generated at different discharge rates.

Rate	Maximum heat generated (kW/m^3)
0.05	1
0.33	7
0.5	14
1	22
2	41

Figure 46: Second order polynomial fit of the maximum heat generated vs the discharge rate.

2.2 ECM

In contrast to the electrochemical model introduced in 2.1, an equivalent circuit model (ECM) was parameterized with the measurement data obtained from the pulse tests (HPPC). The main goal of this model is the prediction of the cell's voltage response for a given current input. Other than in the previous model, the ability to predict the temperature evolution is limited, since the model is only considering a linear temperature exchange with ambient; which is a strong simplification of the situation (considering the test setup inside a temperature chamber). Thus, the overall goal is to combine both models, while harvesting the advantages of either model and obtain a precise prediction of voltage as well as temperature.

The conceptual ECM, that is used to fit to the measurement data looks like the following:

Figure 47: ECM model with two RC-pairs used to represent the electrical cell behavior.

whereas U_{OCV} is the open circuit voltage of the cell measured in the respective test procedure, R_0 is the internal resistance, R_1 , C_1 , R_2 , and C_2 are the charge-transfer resistance and double-layer capacitance of both RC-pairs, respectively. While R_0 represents the instantaneous voltage drop at an applied current pulse; R_1 , C_1 , R_2 and C_2 represent the dynamic behavior of the cell as the current pulse persists. As shown by the equation in the above figure, the parameters of the model are dependent on the state of charge (SoC), the temperature T as well as the applied current I . Thus, these parameters have to be calculated for every measured operation point; e.g. 25 °C, 90 % SoC and 1 C charge/discharge current.

To calculate the model parameters, the measurement data has to be compared to the model structure, which means that the measurement data during a HPPC test represents the cell voltage measured during a current pulse at a certain operation point. Taking into account that the SoC/OCV-curve is known, the voltage-drop over the model parameters can be calculated as follows:

$$U_{drop} = I \left(R_0 + R_1 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{R_1 C_1}} \right) + R_2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{R_2 C_2}} \right) \right)$$

The parameters in the abovementioned equation are then calculated by a least squares algorithm, leading to a simulated voltage response of the cell:

$$U_{cell, sim}(t) = U_{OCV} + I \left(R_{0, fit} + R_{1, fit} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{1, fit}}} \right) + R_{2, fit} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{2, fit}}} \right) \right)$$

The fit quality (root-mean-squared-error RMSE) of every operation point is then calculated to

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (U_{cell, meas} - U_{cell, sim})^2 \right]}$$

With $U_{cell, meas}$ being the measurement data from the HPPC test at a respective operation point (T , SoC, I).

As a target criterion, a voltage difference $|U_{cell,meas} - U_{cell,sim}|$ of 30 mV was considered to evaluate the fit quality of the model.

The following figures show some exemplary fitting results for cell MB003 at an operation point of 10 °C and different SoC-steps mentioned in cell-voltage. The figures show the simulated vs. the measured voltage as well as the difference in voltage.

Figure 49: exemplary model result: simulated vs. measured voltage response and voltage-difference of cell MB003 (10 °C), for a discharge current pulse of 1C.

Figure 48: exemplary model result: simulated vs. measured voltage response and voltage-difference of cell MB003 (10 °C) for a charge current pulse of 1 C.

Both figures show a good accuracy in reproducing the measured voltage response of the cell. The difference in voltages is always below 30 mV.

This model is calculated for every operation point as well as cycling round. Thus, a set of model parameters is calculated not only for different temperatures, SoCs and currents, but also for aging states along the cycle rounds applied to the cells. This will allow to compare the parameters and electrical characteristics predicted by this kind of model with a data-driven model, to assess possible similarities of both models as well as limitations. As mentioned in the periodic report, this kind of model is based upon the interim check-up tests performed with the cells after a cycle round. In contrast however, the data-driven models only consider the cycle-round data, and do

not use the interim test data. Thus, comparing both models and deducing possible mutual performance indicators and limitations can lead to an improved modelling of lithium-ion cells in the future.

The implementation of the developed ECM model in Simulink is shown in the following figure.

Figure 50: ECM model implementation in Matlab/Simulink - the model parameters are chosen based on the operation point (T , SoC) and the current input.

As mentioned in the above figure, the model parameters are chosen from lookup tables for the respective operation point. Thus, a real driving cycle (WLTC) can be simulated with the parameterized model and compared to the real measurement data. In the case shown in the following picture, also cell MB003 was used for the comparison.

Figure 51: real driving cycle applied to cell MB003: simulation vs. measurement.

The above figure shows a good reconstruction of the measured WLTC cycle, whereas the voltage difference gives a good indication about the model accuracy:

Figure 52: real driving cycle applied to cell MB003: voltage delta = simulated - measured voltage.

Figure 52 shows an accurate simulation of the WLTC profile, whereas only towards the end of the cycle the limit of 30 mV ΔU is reached. This might be mainly due to the effect of inaccuracies in the SoC/OCV-curve, which gets increasingly important as the time progresses,

since the SoC calculation in the model is based on Ah-counting. In addition, heating effects that take place during the WLTC profile are not considered in the cell, since the temperature is not fed back to the model. This was mentioned in the beginning of this section since the ECM model is limited in its ability to predict the temperature evolution of the cell. However, in a next step, the satisfying results of the ECM-model in reproducing the electrical response of the cell will be coupled with the electrochemical model with its ability to predict the temperature phenomena, to complement the overall performance of the cell modelling.

3. Thermal Management System

EV's performance are reliant on the battery capabilities. A homogeneous temperature distribution in different temperature ranges is essential for a high vehicle acceleration, a long cell-lifetime and efficient battery charging. Therefore, the TMS must be capable of heating the battery pack at low temperatures in winter and cooling the system in hot conditions during UFC. State of the art TMS, like in the Audi e-tron 55, have a cooling system under the modules. The cooling channels are supplied by a central cooling rail which splits up to channels, one for each row of modules (see Figure 53). The coolant is merged in a collector rail and flows back into the chiller, heat exchanger or is shorted if a heat dissipation of the coolant is not needed.

Figure 53: Audi e-tron 55 battery pack 95 kWh battery pack exploded view (Padgett, 2018)

The one-sided cooling system leads to a temperature gradient over the height of the cells. Furthermore, the lineup of the modules leads to a temperature gradient between the modules since the coolant temperature rises with increasing flow distance. Due to the closed design of the module itself the thermal resistance between the coolant and the cell is increased which results in a less efficient TMS.

In the MARBEL project prismatic cells are used compared to the pouch cells of the Audi e-tron 55 (95 kWh). The difference between these types of cells is shown in Figure 54.

Figure 54: Constructive differences between prismatic cells and pouch cells (Bilgin, et al., 2015)

Prismatic cells have the same layer architecture, but they are wind up to a jelly roll and are placed in a solid cell case. This leads to different thermal conductivities in X-, Y- and Z-directions (X: 5 W/mK; Y: 20 W/mK, Z: 12 W/mK) [https://www.batterydesign.net/thermal-conduction-in-a-cell/; https://www.hotdiskinstruments.com/applications/anisotropy-thermal-conductivity-tests-of-batteries/; “Thermal conductivity inside prismatic lithium-ion cells with dependencies on temperature and external compression pressure” Marco Steinhardt, Elisabeth Irene Gillich, Maximilian Stiegler, Andreas Jossen]. At this time experimental data of the thermal conductivity of the cell was not available and assumptions has to been made. Using the heat flux (\dot{Q}), area (A), thermal conductivity (λ) and half thickness (d), the temperature difference (ΔT) can be calculated:

$$\Delta T = (\dot{Q} \cdot d) / (\lambda \cdot A)$$

The larger the area and the specific thermal conductivity, the lower the temperature difference and therefore thermal resistance. In a first step, a constant heat dissipation of 60 W is assumed, and the different cooling plate arrangements are compared to each other (see Figure 55). The calculation parameters and the results are shown in Table 11.

Figure 55: Cooling concepts based on thermal conductivity and area.

Table 11: Comparison of cooling concepts based on thermal conductivity and area.

	Concept a)	Concept b)	Concept c)
Thermal conductivity	5 W/mK	20 W/mK	12 W/mK
Power dissipation	60 W		
Area	0,022 m ²	0,0045 m ²	0,0097 m ²
Half thickness	0,022 m	0,11 m	0,058 m
Temperature difference	5,94 K	36,6 K	29,8 K

Despite the low thermal conductivity in the Y-direction, concept a) has the highest efficiency, which can be attributed to the size of the surface. Cooling concepts b) and c) have a 6.1 and 5 times larger thermal resistance. Thus, concept a) is the preferred cooling design for prismatic cells.

Considering further requirements for the cooling concept, such as space requirements or assembling complexity, additional options are considered. This results in a solution matrix, which forms the basis for the first 3D simulations.

Figure 56: Solution matrix for different TMS concepts.

Air cooling is not simulated due to the low cooling capacity. The concept of liquid cooling can be divided into upper and lower cooling and lower cooling only. To improve the cooling performance of the lower cooling plate, aluminum fins are placed between the cells and connected to the cooling plate. Several options are available for upper and lower cooling strategy. Vapor chambers increase heat dissipation and can be placed between each cell or on the side of the lined-up cells. These concepts, in principle, requires cooling on top of the cells. The last concept represents immersion cooling with and without gaps between the cells. A dielectric fluid is used to circulate around the cells and absorb the power loss.

To compare the concepts, a module consisting of 6 cells is simulated with STAR-CCM+ for the worst-case scenario. This occurs when the battery pack is fast charged from 10 % SoC to 80 % SoC at an initial temperature of 50 °C. A charging current of 450 A (3 C) flows. The constant cooling power of 400 W is dissipated evenly over the cooling area of the respective concept. The temperature spread within the cell, the temperature difference in the module, the mechanical stresses and the probability of thermal propagation are considered as evaluation parameters. The results are compared in the following table.

Concept	Simulation results	ΔT [K] in cell	ΔT [K] in module	Mechanical stress (swelling)	Thermal propagation probability
Immersion cooling with gaps between cells		8,3	0,1	Special compression pads required	Cooling during thermal runaway possible
Immersion cooling without gaps between cells		19	8,3	High – no compression pads	Thermal propagation probable
Bottom cooling plate with fins		15,4	0,5	High – no compression pads	Thermal propagation probable
Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers between cells		7,8	1,5	Swelling affects vapor chambers	Thermal propagation probable
Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers on side of module		15,7	0,2	High – no compression pads	Thermal propagation probable

Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers on side & fins between cells		9	0,8	High – no compression pads	Thermal propagation propable
Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers on side & aerogel between cells		10,3	0,1	Aerogel take up stress	Aerogel isolating cells from each other
Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers & compression pads between cells		10,6	0,9	Compression pads take up stress	Compression pads isolating cells from each other
Top & bottom cooling with vapor chambers & aerogel between cells		10,7	0,8	Aerogel take up stress	Aerogel isolating cells from each other

Figure 57: Comparison matrix of different cooling concepts.

The single bottom cooling design cannot meet the project requirements. The best performance regarding temperature spread within the cells and at module level can be achieved by the concepts with vapor chambers, immersion cooling and aluminum fins. These concepts offering the potential to suppress thermal propagation. Due to the technical complexity and the environmental impact of the dielectric fluid the immersion cooling is discarded. The vapor chambers exceeding the budget for the cooling system but can be substituted with aluminum fins. This concept is shown in detail in the following figure.

Figure 58: Cooling concept on cell level exploded view.

The figure shows the smallest unit of the cooling system on cell level. On the one side of the cell a compression pad is attached which allows swelling and a homogeneous and defined pretension over the whole lifetime. On the other side and the bottom of the cell thermal pads are placed to fill the unevenness of the battery and ensures a thermal connection to the aluminum fins. These are located at the side of the cell and function as a heat spreader. In contrast to the bottom fin the top fin need spacers to be aligned with the electric terminals.

Figure 59: Cooling concept on module level exploded view without module housing.

A module is built out of six cells in a row. The terminals are electrically connected with busbars which in this case are preliminary parts and do not represent the final design. Thermal pads on the top fins and on the busbars are placed to overcome assembly and manufacturing tolerances and electrically isolate the top cooling rails. These are made from extruded aluminum and are flown through with coolant. The cooling plate on the bottom of the module is a part of the housing of the battery pack. This design combines different functions and help to reduce the weight of the cooling system and the whole battery pack. The different cooling channels are optimized for a low thermal resistance and can take on open cell aluminum foam for better heat dissipation from the cell. To level out smaller tolerances and provide a low thermal resistance, a thermal pad is attached to the cooling plate. During fast charging e.g., the heat dissipation of the cell is passed on to the coolant through the aluminum fins. The high thermal conductivity of the material ensures a low thermal resistance and a homogeneous temperature distribution within the cell. Compared to the Audi e-tron 55 (95 kWh) the missing bottom module housing enhances heat dissipation to the cooling plate.

Compared to the transient simulation at pre-concept level the calculation at module level is done at an operation point that represents a typical traction situation with high cooling demand. This case it is at high speed with power demand of ~140KW (350 A). The dissipated heat is about 5% of the required power. The coolant flow rate is based on a first pack design and the inlet temperature is set to 25°C. The boundary conditions for the simulation are listed in the table below and Figure 60 showing the results.

Table 12: Parameters for thermal simulation on module level.

Use case	High speed driving
Simulation	Stationary
Power loss	40 W + 5.5 W / Busbar
Coolant flow rate & Temperature	1.35 l/min @ 25°C

Figure 60: 3D Simulation of UFC at module level for aluminium fin cooling concept carried out with AVL-FIREM.

The graphs on the left side of the figure showing the min./max./average temperature of each cell, pressure drop in the cooling plate and the thermal resistance (R_{th}). The temperature spread of the cells is 10.2 K (requirement: <10 K). Because of the heat dissipation of the surrounding cells, the cells in the middle of the module showing the highest temperature and the largest temperature spread. The cooling performance can be led back to the low of the cell to cooling plate of approx. 0,156 W/K (requirement: <0,5 K/W) and underlines the cooling performance of this concept.

The last requirement concerns the temperature spread at battery pack level. A transient simulation of UFC use case was not carried out due to missing test data. In addition, a constant high-speed drive with a high-power output was considered. The flow rate results from the operating point of a typical coolant pump at a pressure drop of 500 mbar. The 25 °C coolant inlet temperature is an assumption for this use case and the power loss is typical for Li-Ion cells. For packaging reasons, the modules are in line with the cooling channels as shown in Figure 61. The battery pack is built of 16 rows out of four modules. The simulation parameters are listed in Table 13.

Table 13: Parameters for thermal simulation on battery pack level.

Use case	High speed driving
Simulation	Stationary
Power loss	1092 W (45,5 W per cell & busbar)
Coolant inlet temperature	25 °C
Coolant flow rate	2,03 l/min (32,5 l/min at pack level)

Figure 61: Thermal simulation of modules on battery pack level with module housing.

The figure shows the layout of one row of the battery pack where on the left is the coolant inlet of the top and bottom cooling plates. The hottest module is on the right side because of the heat dissipation of the previous modules. The maximum temperature spread at cell level does not exceed 8,1 K (requirement: 10 K). If the hottest and the coolest modules are compared the temperature spread reaches 6,3 K (requirement: <5 K) which is above the limit and needs improvements. These could be achieved by the integration of the aluminum foam. At the time of the simulation no data was available from the practical tests and could not be considered in the simulation. The max. temperature spread at battery level is 6.3 (requirement: <5 K) considering the whole battery pack an overall pressure drop of 312 mbar (requirement: < 500 mbar) with evenly distributed volume flow in each parallel channel is achieved. With the improvement of the temperature spread at module level the cooling system design meets all requirements of the project.

4. Conclusions

Battery cells' performance has been validated in the relevant environment in-house in EUT and THI laboratories. As a results of these MARBEL consortium in-house analyses, **cell performance is found to be well in-line with manufacturer specifications.** Additionally, further key information has been obtained. The welding seam has been found to rapidly heat at high discharge currents (300 A) and the continues UFC protocol to severely impact on the cell life, with a severe degradation detected, requiring adapting the UFC protocol as an immediate measure ongoing.

In terms of cell modelling, an electrochemical model has been validated to obtain the heat generated at different discharge rates. The output of this model can be used to properly design the cooling system. Additionally, an ECM was parameterized to predict the cell's voltage response for a given input current. Combining both models will allow to obtain a precise response in terms of temperature and voltage.

This deliverable is based on a specific type of cell and the effort and work done by all the partners involved in the process will be used for its applicability in the new cells that will be considered for this project in the next stages.

5. References

- Bilgin, B., Magne, P., Malysz, P., Yang, Y., Pantelic, V., Preindl, M., . . . Emadi, A. (2015, 06 01). Making the Case for Electrified Transportation. *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*.
- Guo, J., Li, Y., Meng, J., Pedersen, K., Gurevich, L., & Stroe, D.-I. (2022). *Understanding the mechanism of capacity increase during early cycling*. Aalborg, Denmark . Chengdu, China: Journal of Energy Chemistry.
- Padgett, M. (2018, April 20). *Green Car Reports*. Retrieved 2022, from https://www.greencarreports.com/news/1116347_audi-details-battery-for-2019-e-tron-electric-suv
- Vanaclocha, C. (2021). *Comparative study of three electrochemical cell models for the CFD simulation of a battery module*. Valencia: Universitat Politècnica de València.